

Research Article

Factors Associated With Adolescent Pregnancy among Secondary School Students in Ogbia Local Government Area of Bayelsa State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study investigated the factors associated with Adolescent Pregnancy among Secondary School Students in Ogbia, Bayelsa State, Nigeria. Three Research questions were asked alongside, 3 corresponding hypotheses with emphasis on age, level of study, and religion. The study adopted the descriptive survey design. The population of the study consisted of all the secondary school adolescents in Bayelsa State. The study adopted the multi-stage sampling procedure to select 300 secondary school female adolescents. The instrument for data collection was the questionnaire designed by the researcher made of sections A and B which emphasized socio-demographic and objectives based questions respectively. The instruments were validated by 3 research experts. The reliability of the instrument was 0.89 using cronbach-alpha. Some of the findings of the study were; there existed a significant relationship ($X^2_{cal}=37.562$, $X^2_{crit}= 0.464$) between Age and the Prevalence of Adolescent Pregnancy. There exists no significant relationship between level of study and the prevalence of adolescent pregnancy ($F_{cal}= 0.200$, $F_{crit}= 0.819$). There existed a significant relationship between Religion and prevalence of adolescent pregnancy. Based on the findings of the study some recommendation were made which included, repositioning health education programme in the school curriculum, religious organization should organize programmes to make youths understand the consequences of adolescent pregnancy.

KEYWORDS: Adolescent Pregnancy, Secondary School students, Ogbia, Bayelsa State.

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Introduction

Pregnancy is an important period in a woman's life and so demands physical, social, physiological and emotional preparation to enable the woman meet the extra demands on her by the developing foetus. Adolescent girl may become pregnant as a result of different factors. Some adolescent girls become pregnant while involved in long-term dating relationships, sex debut, due to rape among others. The fact simply remains that all adolescent pregnancies are the result of sexual activity, whether wanted or unwanted. Factors, such as; age, level of study, religion, education level of parents, place of residence, and friend of the opposite sex could result in adolescent pregnancy. Xie, etal, (2011); Olamide, (2006) Opined that today, puberty occurs much earlier in adolescents, and first time sexual encounters are taking place at younger ages, resulting in more sexually experienced adolescents and prevalence of adolescent pregnancy. Nwankwo (2011) noted that, adolescent pregnancy occurs in younger woman under the age of 20 years and reported that adolescent pregnancy depends on the age at first sexual initiation.

Hogan and Kitagawa, (2008) noted that, instead of career and educational success, adolescents believe that they must reach adulthood another way, specifically through early pregnancy. It also corroborates the view of Van, and Eijk, (2007 that, adolescent pregnancy has become a national epidemic, partly because more and more adolescents who give birth decide to keep and raise their children rather than focusing on their studies. However, in the view of Santelli, Lowry and Brener, (2000) the prevalence of adolescent pregnancy can be attributed to educational level. This finding also negates that of Olamide, (2006) who specified that adolescent pregnancy is associated with low level of education. This showed that, the proportion of respondents believing their religion's scripture in the word of God predicted higher adolescent pregnancy rates showing non-significant association between the religion of the respondents and prevalence of adolescent pregnancy. Robinson, (1999) stated that cultural traditions may also have influence on the acceptability of early pregnancy on the family structure. This has being the case in some communities, especially in some parts of Nigeria and other countries in Africa. Girls who get pregnant often have mother who gave birth in their teens. Parents of teen mothers and fathers are often considered by their teens to have "permissive attitudes" regarding premarital sex and pregnancy. There are also cultural differences in the values placed on having children. This finding is also at variance with that of Achouwa, (2000) who stated that religious beliefs are common causes of adolescent pregnancy.

According to Kinanee, (1994). The environment shapes the personality development of the adolescents and the immediate environment of an individual is the family which is the first external world. The report of Blair, Jones and Simon, (2002); Nigerian Population Council, (2005); that, adolescents from polygamous homes where the children in the homes are too many for the man to cater for, the children resort to indulging themselves in premarital sex in order to earn their living this leading them to becoming pregnant. However, Manlove *et al.* (2002) reported that, adolescent living in poverty stricken neighbourhood were more apt to engage in sexual intercourse, often leading to adolescent pregnancy and childbirth. The report of this study also supports that of Rothenberg and Weissman, (2002); Brindis and Philliber, (2003); who documented that in an environment where there is lack of positive role models and impoverished living situation, adolescent particularly the females, decide to become pregnant or they 'drift' into pregnancy, as this decision appears to be their best option. However, Surd, (2000) stated that, educating families about sex and contraception can affect the adolescent likelihood of becoming pregnant, the residence notwithstanding.

Coley and Chase-lansdale, (1998) who documented that one third of adolescents' mothers drop out of school before pregnancy occurs. The finding of this study is also in line with that of Mchunu, Peltzer, Tutshana and Seutlwadi (2012) in Coley *et al.* (1998) who noted that adolescent pregnancy was associated with such factors as parents educational level. Olamide, (2006) stated that, there is also likelihood of peers mounting pressure on their innocent friends or young ones' who have carelessly become pregnant and given birth to babies in the past may put pressure on them to do the same thing by giving them false advantages attached to it.

Age and Prevalence of Adolescent Pregnancy

Age is a crucial factor in the definition of an adolescent. An adolescent is a person who is between 13-19 years old; those aged between 10-19 years and persons between 12-19 years (The International Seminar on Adolescent and Fertility in Africa, 2007 and World Health Organization, 1993). Specifically, Turner (2004) refers to adolescent as persons (boys and girls) between ages 12-19 years. Adolescent is an individual within the ages of 13-19 years (Makinwa, 2000). Physical development in girls is not complete until 14 years. The concept of adolescent is generic referring to both boys and girls. In this study, adolescent refers exclusively to the girl-child who is in the secondary school.

Turner (2004): Said one of the first signs of adolescence is the sudden growth sprout in boys, which occurs between the age of 12-19 years and continues approximately for two years while in girls they have a similar two years sprout which generally begins at twelve

years, they gain seven to twelve meters in growth within those period. Adolescent pregnancy results when the adolescent involves in unprotected sexual intercourse within the ages of 13 and 19 years. Statistics reveals that 13 million children are born to adolescents annually worldwide, about 9% in developing nations. As a matter of fact, Nigeria has the highest cases of adolescent pregnancy. Nwankwo, (2011), stated that adolescent pregnancy is a pregnancy in a young woman (adolescent) who has not reached her 20th birthday, when the pregnancy ends, regardless of whether the woman is married or unmarried.

Bennet and Brown, (1985) in Myles, (2000) defined adolescent pregnancy as a pregnancy in a young girl between the ages of 13 - 19 years of age while it is regarded as an underage girl becoming pregnant in the United States i.e. before her 18th birth day (Cannon, 2008). The Federal Ministry of Health through the National Training Manual on Adolescent Health and Development, (2001); defined adolescent pregnancy as pregnancy which occur below the age of 18 years.

Action Health Incorporated in Makinwa (2000), opined that most adolescents get pregnant unprepared which is due to lack of proper sexuality education as more than three quarters of Nigerian girls have sexual intercourse before the age of 20 years. Adolescent pregnancy occurs in girls within this age bracket. The adolescent period in the view of Derek (2005), is a period which the individual is no longer regarded as a child, but he or she is accepted as an adult by social norms. It is a period of transition from childhood to adulthood and the adolescent resumes responsibilities; puberty is the first stage of the adolescence.

Adolescence refers to the transitory period of an individual, inevitably passes through in her growth from childhood to adulthood or maturity. The World Health Organization (WHO, 1989) defined adolescence as the age period between 10-19 years for either married or unmarried sexes. Adolescence is a period of transformation because the child experiences what is called the sprout where the child changes from child to mature adult.

According to Andrew, (2001), the adolescence period is that span of a young person's life between the obvious onset of puberty and the completion of bone growth. Ebiye, (2004) in Andrew, (2001) Stated that by conservative estimate, about 85% of adolescent pregnancies are unwanted. This is hardly surprising when one considers the social circumstances of girls in this age group. Most adolescent pregnancies are accidental and occur when young girls are not adequately or properly informed about conception and the risk of pregnancy.

According to Iwundu, (1995); maternal age is very significant for procreation to take place. It is advisable that adolescents should not get pregnant below the age of 20 years of age. It is a known fact that a girl who becomes pregnant often suffers from complications. This is because the various organs for conceptions and the labour stages are not developed. According to Briggs (1995) adolescents have greater risks of dying during pregnancy and childbirth than woman of 20 years and above. They are more likely to have increased pregnancy problems such as raised blood pressure, anaemia and difficulty in labour due to cephalopelvic disproportion, sometimes leads to death of both the mother and the child.

Olamide (2006) and Nwankwo (2011), stated that adolescent pregnancy is a pregnancy in a young woman (adolescent) who has not reached her 20th birthday, when the pregnancy ends, regardless of whether the woman is married or unmarried. In Nigeria adolescents between the ages of 13-19 years contribute to overall fertility rates (WHO, 2000) Female adolescent's 15-19 years of age that represented 20% of all sample of women contributed 13.7% of female sample that are pregnant during the Nigerian fertility survey in (1981-1982). The studies also reveal that half of the adolescents gave birth in teens about 12% of them gave birth before 15. Farber, (2003) found that about 40% of girls who first had intercourse at age 13 or 14 indicated involuntary or unwanted intercourse with an older partner.

Between 1983 and 1995, the proportion of adolescent females who first had sex at 14 years old or younger practically doubled (National Campaign to Prevent Adolescent Pregnancy, 2003). Adolescent whose mothers gave birth as adolescents or who have pregnant siblings are also more likely to engage in early sexual intercourse and became parents as well (Manlove, 2002, Xie, etal, 2011).

Sexual abuse may alter perceptions about sexual behavior, leading to an abuse of adolescent, especially females, to initial sex at an earlier age and have more partners (Saewyc, Magee, and Pettingell, 2004). McCullough & Scherman (1991) speculated that some adolescent pregnancies possibly resulted from unresolved feeling and behavior associated with earlier sexual abuse.

A survey carried out by the International Planned Parenthood Federation (IPPF) in Briggs (1997) showed that three quarters of adolescents fewer than 15 and half of those over 15 years have no access to reproductive health information. According to Pasman, (2000) 60% of girls between 15 - 19 years in Nairobi, Kenya knew nothing about contraception. Kenya has the highest total fertility rate (8.1%) in the World and Nigeria has (6.6%)

(Population Reference Bureau, 1999). Lack of knowledge about contraception and fertility can lead to unwanted pregnancy at the adolescence age.

Level of Study and Prevalence of Adolescent Pregnancy

According to Briggs (1992), 68.3% of pregnant adolescent interviewed at antenatal clinics have no contraceptive knowledge. Most adolescents lack information on sexuality and contraception, as most of the education that is presented on this matter is limited (Arai, 2003; Bankole, Ahmed, Ouedraogo, Neema and Konyani, 2007). The study by Kaufman, De Wet and Stadler (2001) indicated that there was a slightly lower level of knowledge about modern methods of contraception among adolescents. Morake (2011) indicated that in the reports of the Department of Health of the Limpopo province, adolescents were reportedly not good contraceptive users, because they might not admit to being sexually active. Other studies reported that the adolescent had inaccurate knowledge on the use of contraceptive (Bankole, 2007). It implies that supplying adequate information about sexual behaviours and contraceptives to adolescents should be of paramount importance. Adolescent believes that pregnancy cannot result from the initial act of intercourse, but only by repeated sexual encounters. Adolescents are further surrounded by sexual images and messages, which imply that sexual activities are the norm (Mwaba, 2000).

The findings by Ritcher and Mlambo (2005) stated that adolescent pregnancies resulted from lack of knowledge about contraception and many other misconceptions. It was indicated that injectable contraceptives results in weight gain and watery discharges, while contraceptives pills were only taken when they planned sexual intercourse or only after the engagement because it could prevent them from becoming pregnant when used in that way.

The World Health Organization (WHO, 1995) recently classified poverty as a disease. Its harmful effects on the lives of the growing ones, particularly the adolescents, are too numerous to mention. In a poor socio-economic community, illiteracy, street hawking or trading, prostitution, rape and indeed adolescent pregnancy are very common features.

Olamide, (2006) added that, most girls who fall victims of adolescents' pregnancy come from lower socio-economic group. Poverty is also an associated factor for adolescent pregnancy, often leading to poorer outcomes for adolescent mothers (Tripp & Viner, 2005). Instead of career and educational success they believe that they must reach adulthood another way, specifically through early pregnancy (Hogan and Kitagawa, 2008).

According to Santelli, Lowry, and Brener, 2000; data supports the fact that the prevalence of adolescent pregnancy is on the increase. This can be attributed to the effects that a lower socio-economic status, namely, one's living environment, education level and future opportunities. Therefore, low socio-economic status of an adolescent can increase the risk of adolescent pregnancy. According to Van *et al.* (2007) adolescent pregnancy has become a national epidemic, partly because more and more adolescents who give birth decide to keep and raise their children.

For the young mother, the risks of child bearing do not necessarily end with delivery; it may be catastrophic for young girls in secondary school or university. Early pregnancy usually terminates her chance of going back to school. For examples, in Kenya, pregnancy forces about 10% of the girls enrolled in secondary schools to drop out each year (Murangu, 2000). Similarly, findings from Nigerian study involving 127 pregnant school girls have shown that 52% were "too ashamed to return" 15% could not return because of parents' refusal to pay their tuition while 8% were forced to marry (Nicholas, 1999; Murangu, 2000).

Research findings have revealed that a female who has her first child during adolescent period is most likely to have low education and less income, which would affect her socio-economic development. As a result, she would be susceptible to ill health, poverty economic dependency in the society (Olamide, 2006). Pregnant adolescents often find themselves in situations they never prepared, either financially or emotionally. Many of them have drop out of school, leave home and become dependent upon public welfare friends and well-wishers. Early repeat or subsequent pregnancies further expose adolescent mothers to more economic hardships, child abuse and abandonment.

Religion and Prevalence of Adolescent Pregnancy

Robinson, (1999) stated that cultural traditions may also have influence on the acceptability of early pregnancy on the family structure. This has been the case in some communities, especially in some parts of Nigeria and other countries in Africa. Girls who get pregnant often have mother who gave birth in their teens. Parents of teen mothers and fathers are often considered by their teens to have "permissive attitudes" regarding premarital sex and pregnancy. There are also cultural differences in the values placed on having children. Thompson, (2000) found that among 300 adolescents (150 white and 150 Black), blacks expressed stronger beliefs than the white that children promote greater personal security, marital success, and approval of others.

Achouwa, (2000) stated that cultural beliefs are common causes of adolescent pregnancy for this view that females are not permanent members of the family, this account for the reason why female children are given out for marriage at a tender age which lead to adolescent pregnancies. The society or the parents determine age at marriage in Nigeria culture as quoted in Egbe, (2001), girls, are allowed to marry in their adolescent (at about thirteen, 13) years in the continue process these girls get pregnant.

Statement of the Problem

There is no provision of the education law in Nigeria that allows pregnant students in secondary schools. This has a serious implication for school population by the pregnant adolescent girl-child. To an adolescent the risks of child bearing became catastrophic for the young girl in secondary school and early pregnancy usually terminates her chances of going back to school. Sometimes, adolescent pregnancy results among adolescents who make friends with members of the opposite sex based on self-identity, self-definition and self-interest. Adolescent pregnancy results in poor academic performance in school and a girl might have to drop out of school. Adolescent pregnancy and early motherhood is associated with poverty, most girls who fall victims of pregnancy come from lower socio-economic group. It has been observed that adolescents who engaged in sexual behaviour that puts them at the risk of not only having unwanted pregnancy but also puts them at the risk of having sexually transmitted infections and premarital pregnancy. A girl who becomes pregnant at an early age is believed to have lost her self-esteem or value. Adolescent pregnancy is also associated with health problems such as; pregnancy induces hypertension, anaemia, surgical operation and maternal death. This makes it imperative to determine the prevalence of adolescent pregnancy and associated factors among secondary schools' students in Ogbia Local Government Area in Bayelsa.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study was to investigate the Factors Associated with Adolescent Pregnancy among Secondary School Students, in Ogbia local Government Area, Bayelsa State.

Research Questions and Hypotheses

The following Research questions and Corresponding Hypotheses were proposed to guide the study:

Research Questions

This study will attempt to provide answers to the following questions:

1. What is the influence of age on the prevalence of adolescent pregnancy among secondary schools in Ogbia Local Government Area of Bayelsa State?
2. What is the influence of level of study on the prevalence of adolescent pregnancy among secondary schools in Ogbia Local Government Area of Bayelsa State?
3. What is the influence of religion on the prevalence of adolescent pregnancy among secondary schools in Ogbia Local Government Area of Bayelsa State?

Research Hypotheses

H01: There is no significant relationship between age and the prevalence of adolescent pregnancy among secondary schools in Ogbia Local Government Area of Bayelsa State.

H02: There is no significant relationship between level of study and the prevalence of adolescent pregnancy among secondary schools in Ogbia Local Government Area of Bayelsa State.

H03: There is no significant relationship between religion and the prevalence of adolescent pregnancy among secondary schools in Ogbia Local Government Area of Bayelsa State.

Area for the Study

The study is carried out in Ogbia Local Government Area of Bayelsa State. Ogbia Local Government Area shares common boundary with Nembe local Government Area at the South, Yenagoa Local Government Area at the North, Southern Ijaw Local Government Area at the East and Abua-Odual Local Government Area of Rivers State at the West. The people are mainly farmers, fishermen/women, small time hunters, sand-dredgers and Civil servants. The major medium of communication is Ogbia dialect and the English Language. There are secondary and primary schools in the area including public and private schools.

Research Design

The study adopted the descriptive survey design. In this study, the researcher collected data from the population of unmarried adolescent female students in secondary schools in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State and described certain features without manipulating any variable in the study.

Population for the Study

The population for the study consisted of all the secondary school Adolescents in Bayelsa State, Nigeria.

Sample and Sampling Techniques

The sample for study was three hundred (300) adolescent females in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State. Four wards (ward I, ward 2, ward 6 and ward 9) among 13 political wards in the Local Government Area were selected. Where Government secondary school Ogbia Town; Community secondary school, Kolo Town; Community Secondary School, Otuasega Town; Community secondary school, Otuokpoti Town; and Community Secondary School, Onuebum Town were selected via simple random sampling.

The systematic random sampling technique was adopted to select 33 students from JS1, JS2 and JS3 of all the selected schools.

Validity of the Instrument

The instrument was validated by three specialists in the Departments of Human Kinetics, Health and Safety Education, Mathematics, and Measurement and Evaluation of the Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Port Harcourt. The initial draft of the instrument was presented to the supervisor and these specialists for critical examination specifically for face and content validation. Comments, corrections, suggestions and advice were used rewrite the final copy.

Instrument for Data Collection

The instrument for collection of data in this study was the Prevalence of Adolescent Pregnancy Questionnaire. The questionnaire consisted of two sections; A and B. Section A concentrated on the socio-demographic characteristics of respondents' information such as age, sex, marital status, level of education, religion, place of residence and parents level of education. Section B dealt with questions formulated based on the objectives of the study.

Reliability of the Instrument

The reliability of the instrument was tested using Cronbach alpha with the use of SPSS. A reliability of 0.89 was obtained, which is appropriate for the study.

Results

Table 1. Chi-squared test showing relationship between age and prevalence of adolescent pregnancy

Age	Prevalence of adolescent pregnancy		Total	Df	X ² -value	P-values	Decision
	Yes	No					
10-14	13(30.9%)	29(69.1%)	42	4	37.562	0.464	Rejected
15-19	183(73.8%)	65(26.2%)	248				
Total	196	94	290				

*Significant

Table 1, showed that the X²-value of 37.562 at 0.05 significant level is greater than the P-value (0.464). Hence, the hypothesis that states that there is no significant relationship between age and the prevalence of adolescent pregnancy among secondary schools in Ogbia Local Government Area of Bayelsa State is rejected. This implies that there is a significant relationship between the two variables.

Table 2: One-Way ANOVA of level of study and prevalence of adolescent pregnancy

Source	SS	Df	MSS	F-cal	F-tab	Decision
Between groups	2.150	2	1.075	0.200	0.819	Accepted
Within groups	1482.115	276	5.370			
Total	1484.265	278				

*P<0.05

Table 2 shows that the F-calculated (0.200) at 0.05 level of significance was lesser than the F-tabulated (0.819). Therefore, the null hypothesis that states that there is no significant relationship between level of study and prevalence of adolescent pregnancy among secondary schools in Ogbia Local Government Area of Bayelsa State is accepted.

Table 3: Chi-squared test showing relationship between religion and prevalence of adolescent pregnancy

Religion	Prevalence of adolescent pregnancy		Total	Df	X ² -value	P-values	Decision
	Yes	No					
Christianity	128(65.3%)	68(34.7%)	196	8	12.256	0.140	Rejected
Islam	17(65.4%)	9(34.6%)	26				
Paganism	4(57.1%)	3(42.9%)	7				
Traditional religion	45(80.4%)	11(19.6%)	56				
Total	194	91	284				

*Significant

Table 3 showed that the X²-value of 12.256 at 0.05 significant level was greater than the P-value (0.140), showing that there is a significant relationship. The null hypothesis that stated that there is no significant relationship between religion and the prevalence of adolescent pregnancy among secondary schools in Ogbia Local Government Area of Bayelsa State is therefore rejected.

Discussion of Findings

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant relationship between age and the prevalence of adolescent pregnancy among secondary schools.

The result of the finding in Table 1 Shows a chi-value $X^2 = 37.562$, $P = 0.464$, of 4 at 0.05 alpha level of significance. The result indicates that there is a significant relationship between age and the prevalence of adolescent pregnancy. This relationship found in this study could be attributed to the fact that, at the age of becoming adolescent, there is tendency for a curiosity for sexual intercourse and sexual exploitation; and most of these adolescents indulge in sexual activities were without adequate knowledge on how to prevent pregnancy, lack boldness to negotiate contraceptive use and due to strong need for hetero-sexual relationships, there is peer conforming and acceptance. Hence, these would have contributed to significant relationship between age and the prevalence of adolescent pregnancy.

This result is in line with that of the Xie *et al.* (20011); Olamide, (2006); who opined that today, puberty occurs much earlier in adolescents, and first time sexual encounters are taking place at younger ages, resulting in more sexually experienced adolescents and

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prevalence of adolescent pregnancy. This finding is also in keeping with what Nwankwo (2011) noted that, adolescent pregnancy occurs in younger woman under the age of 20 years and reported that adolescent pregnancy depends on the age of first sexual initiation. The similarities between the previous studies and the present one is hardly surprising when one considers the social circumstances of individuals in this age group. Most adolescent pregnancies are accidental and occur when young girls are not adequately or properly informed about conception and the risk of pregnancy. However, Iwundu, (1995) documented that maternal age is very significant for procreation to take place.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant relationship between level of study and the prevalence of adolescent pregnancy among secondary schools

The result of the finding in Table 2 shows ANOVA, $F =$ calculated value of 0.200, $F =$ table value of 0.819, of 2 at 0.05 alpha level of significance. The finding shows that there is no significant relationship between level of study and prevalence of adolescent pregnancy. This finding might be due to the fact that before some adolescents get to the level of education where they will be given a comprehensive sexuality education, they would have had a background knowledge which would have given them some misconceptions about pregnancy. Such misconceptions are seen in the believe that, pregnancy cannot result from the initial act of intercourse, but only by repeated sexual encounters.

This finding is in agreement with what Hogan and Kitagawa, (2008) noted that, instead of career and educational success, adolescents believe that they must reach adulthood another way, specifically through early pregnancy. It also corroborates the view of Van, (2007) that, adolescent pregnancy has become a national epidemic, partly because more and more adolescents who give birth decide to keep and raise their children rather than focusing on their studies. However, the finding of the presents study is at variance with the view of Santelli, Lowry and Brener, (2000) that, the prevalence of adolescent pregnancy can be attributed to educational level. This finding also negates that of Olamide, (2006) who specified that adolescent pregnancy is associated with low level of education. Some reasons can be adduced for such divergent findings. In the first place, the above studies were conducted some years back and so, may not have taken cognizance of the new trend of things. However, the finding of the present study which has divergent result may have been affected by the current/new trend of things among the adolescent age group.

Hypothesis 3

There is no significant relationship between religion and the prevalence of adolescent pregnancy among secondary schools.

The result of the finding in Table 3 Shows a chi-value $X^2= 12.256$, $P= 0.140$, of 8 at 0.05 alpha level of significance. The result shows that there is a significant relationship between religion and the prevalence of adolescent pregnancy among secondary schools. This finding might be due to the fact that, the religious adolescents in the study area had no regard for their religion in terms of sexual matters.

This finding showed that, the proportion of respondents believing their religion's scripture in the word of God predicted higher adolescent pregnancy rates showing non-significant association between the religion of the respondents and prevalence of adolescent pregnancy. The similarities between the two studies might be due to the fact that, there are similar characters between the respondents of the above study and the present one. However, the result of the present study differs from that of Robinson, (1999) whose result revealed that the adolescent pregnancy depends on religion. This finding is also at variance with that of Achouwa, (2000) who stated that religious beliefs are common causes of adolescent pregnancy. The variation between the above studies and the present one might be due to the fact that the above studies were conducted in study areas different from where the present study was conducted.

Recommendations

The results of this research necessitated that certain measures should be taken in order to prevent adolescent pregnancy. The researcher therefore offers the following recommendations which can be of tremendous use if adhered to.

- 1 Government should intensify the teaching of sex education programme in the school curriculum; this would help to reduce the rate of adolescent pregnancy in the area.
- 2 Religious organization should organize programmes in order to bring up youths in the fear of God; in other words, activities that encourage an understanding of the ideal role men and women should be emphasised in religious gatherings.
- 3 Parents should discourage early marriage in all traditions in the Local Government Area and the girl child should be protected optimally to avoid rape and its attendant consequences.
- 4 Government should employ Health Educators/Guidance Counselors and post them to schools for educating/counseling the adolescents on moral behaviours.

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